

6G SNS

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OPS**

Digital Innovation Hubs (DHI) to strengthen knowledge exchange with SNS community and collaboration

Impact Assessment
and Facilitation Action (IAFA)

Event Series #1

5 October 2023
14.00 - 16.00 (Online)

This event is part of a series of actions in the scope of SNS OPS CSA targeting relevant partnerships, initiatives and associations to raise awareness about the work of SNS JU and its projects to explore synergies regarding the expectations and developments of SNS technology and, ultimately, advance towards the digitalisation of European industry, economy and society.

Synopsis and Agenda

The first IAFA event, Digital Innovation Hubs (DIH), to strengthen knowledge exchange with the SNS community and collaboration event, occurred online on Thursday, 5 October 2023.

The DIH aims to facilitate the digitalisation of European industry in the context of the Digital Europe Programme. [SCoDIHNet](#) (Smart Connectivity Digital Innovation Hub Network) is a network of DIHs with expertise in Smart Connectivity (5G/6G, IoT, Security).

DIHs aim to develop the links between end users (industry) and technology providers, of which SNS JU projects are considered key sources. To this end, various initiatives are being developed focusing on replicability, mapping of technology providers and end-user requirements.

The **replicability initiative** aims to facilitate the reuse of use cases/solutions developed by SNS projects by compiling them in a regularly updated catalogue from which DIHs could pick up use cases and solutions that fit their customers. The **mapping initiative** aims to map all technology providers, testbeds and DIHs at the regional level to foster cooperation among stakeholders working in the same region, thus facilitating innovation development with end-user customers. Lastly, **end-user requirements** are being collected to feed the SNS RIA and work plan, as DIHs are very close to end users.

Vertical industries involved

Main Takeaways

Scalability and interoperability are essential to fulfil the EU's strategy to create more connected and efficient innovation ecosystems to support the scaling of companies, encourage innovation and stimulate cooperation among national, regional and local authorities.

SCoDIHNet and European Digitalisation Strategy

SCoDIHNet is working to facilitate the digitalisation of the European industry process through several catalogues about IoT/5G technical platforms and mapped smart connectivity technology providers with Digital Innovation Hubs at the regional level.

The technology provides a catalogue that aims to facilitate cooperation between stakeholders at the regional level, encompassing many organisations (technology providers, users, DIHs, test beds, Gaia-X hubs and policymakers).

Main pillars of SCoDIHNet strategy

- ① Support DIHs in the Digitalisation of the European Industry by providing a number of services and catalogues
- ① Collect end users' needs and technical requirements to feed the SNS strategic agenda
- ① Develop cooperation with European organisations to help DIHs better cooperate with key stakeholders
- ① Facilitate cooperation between Technology providers, DIHs and Integrators at the regional level to develop local collaboration between stakeholders
- ① Provide criteria and guidelines to discuss scalability and replicability from a technological, market and stakeholder perspective.
- ① Create a questionnaire collecting information about scalability and replicability to disseminate among projects.
- ① Create a replicability and scalability assessment tool to increase projects' efficiency and maximise result impacts.

Establishing a Common Approach to Support DIHs During Their Path

METHODIH¹ is a methodology for DIHs aiming at supporting DIHs with a structured approach, providing four basic tools to define a sustainable offering matching their customer-base needs:

- ① the Service Portfolio Analysis, to set up DIH's service portfolio per a common structure, to encourage collaboration among DIHs and to make it easier for new services to be defined to build a robust portfolio. The Service Portfolio analysis is performed by the DIH, starting from a structured approach called D-BEST analysis. The framework has been conceived for the DIHs to define their "AS-IS" service portfolio and identify the gaps to be filled in their offering. Services are classified according to a 3-level taxonomy; the following figure depicts the 2nd-level taxonomy of this reference model.

1. Razzetti S, Gusmeroli S, Terzi S, Sassanelli C. METHOdology for DIH: Adding the Remote Macro-Class to the D-BEST Reference Model. Proceedings <http://ceur-ws.org> ISSN. 2022;1613:0073.

- ① The Customer Journey analysis is offered to understand typical ecosystem stakeholders' needs, expectations, and interaction procedures. Six distinct customer categories (Technology Provider, Technology User, Student, Policy Maker, Start-up, Experimenter) are provided with customisable templates consisting of five-step journeys representing the essential stages of the digital transformation process. The identification of blocking spots where DIH should assist the client is a critical stage in this research.
- ① the Digital Transformation Pipelines, in order to connect demand (customer needs) with the offering (service portfolio) and to describe the customer engagement with the DIH and the measures to be taken to implement the evolutionary pathway and overcome bottlenecks in a structured manner. The time component is critical in the definition of service pipelines. Pipelines are transformed into success stories when adapted to unique customer profiles, reinforcing the catalogue of best practices.
- ① the Business and Governance Model, to guide the DIH in defining a model to describe its business, considers the complexity of its customer base and a multistakeholder network, including sustainability for cross-regional activities. One specific dimension is Governance, which considers the complexity of the collaborative DIH's activities.

DIH4INDUSTRY for European Manufacturing

Developed in partnership with the European Commission's Digital Innovation Hubs tool, [DIH4INDUSTRY](#) is a platform aiming to establish and oversee a network of Digital Innovation Hubs that specialise in regional manufacturing. It serves as a central platform for DIH professionals and policymakers to determine active EC DIHs in the manufacturing sector, their locations, the projects they back, and the services they offer for the digital evolution of the EU's manufacturing industry.

DIH4INDUSTRY
The EU Network of DIHs in the Manufacturing domain

Home Ecosystem About Sign In

The Ecosystem of DIHs active in the Digital Transformation of European Manufacturing Industry

SIGN UP HERE

DIHs Community
111
VISIT

D BEST Marketplace
895
VISIT

Indicator	Value
D	9%
B	25%
E	27%
S	16%
T	23%

IoT Digital Innovation Hub

The [IoT Digital Innovation Hub](#) aims to develop groundbreaking projects with the most advanced technologies, promoting innovative IoT solutions and services that can boost companies' competitiveness (especially SMEs).

DIH's main pillars are:

- 1. Contextualise the role of Digital Innovation Hubs in Economy 4.0
- 2. Justify the need for efficient growth strategies
- 3. Describe SMART (Specific, Measurable, Achievable, Relevant, Time-bound) Goals

Replicability and Scalability Assessment Tool

The **Replicability and Scalability Assessment Tool** aims to map and assess exploitable results during project life against the technical, market, stakeholder, data, IPR, and regulatory dimensions. This process is accomplished through several phases:

1. Define actions to foster replicability (early adopters involvement, clustering, open calls, scientific publications, public presentations, networking events).
2. Identify KPIs for each dimension and a weighting method.
3. Design tool
4. Check results with selected projects.
5. Use platforms that can support the replication of project results (IoT Catalogue, Horizon Results Platform, NG IoT Catalogue, etc.)

Based on these criteria, a catalogue is currently being developed with existing use cases/solutions designed by IoT Large Scale Pilot projects and 5GPPP's Phase 3 experimental projects, currently containing 1200 use cases/solutions/enablers.

Based on these measurement criteria, three main ranges of replicability have been identified, which will be perfected and put into implementation in the following months

- ① High level of replicability: $61 < LR < 80$
- ① Good level of replicability: $31 < LR < 60$
- ① Low level of replicability: $00 < LR < 30$

Expected results are a replicability and scalability tool, reports about the initiative, and workshop presentations involving the European Commission.

Replicability and Scalability Assessment Tool for SNS JU

This tool is also being tested among SNS JU projects, with 31 out of 35 SNS JU R&I Phase 1 projects developing replicable solutions which will be of interest for the replicability initiative. Given an average 2-3 years duration and a follow-up exploitation phase, the Replicability and Scalability Assessment Tool could be used to measure the evolution of the Replicability Level.

In this sense, DIHs have the key role of accelerating the development and replicability of these technologies at the industrial level and bridging end-user requirements gaps if necessary.

Resources

DIH4INDUSTRY - The EU Network of DIHs in the Manufacturing Industry.

DIH - IoT Digital Innovation Hub.

SCoDIHNet - Smart Connectivity Digital Innovation Hub Network.

White Paper - A Replicability and Scalability Assessment tool, Release 1.0.